

A Case Series of Complicated Chronic Otitis Media**Karnadev Solanki¹, Hiren Doshi², Tej Dashadiya³, Anand Bhatasana⁴, Bhautik Mangukiya⁵, Disha Makwani⁶**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Narendra Modi Medical College²Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Narendra Modi Medical College^{3,4}rd Year Resident, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Narendra Modi Medical College⁵2nd year Resident, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Narendra Modi Medical College⁶Reader, Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry, Karnavati School of Dentistry, Karnavati University

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Abstract:**Introduction:** With the advent of antibiotics, complications of otitis media have become less common. It is crucial for physicians to recognize otitis media and treat its complications early. Herein, we present our institution's experience with patients who required emergency surgical intervention for complications of otitis media.**Methods:** All 15 patients of COM with intra or extra cranial complication who were admitted in the Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Narendra Modi Medical College Ahmedabad, from April 2023 to April 2024 were included in this retrospective analytic study.**Results:** Out of 15 patients 6 were male patients and 9 were female patients. We have done HRCT temporal bone in all 15 patients and only 2 patients required MRI BRAIN scan. 13 patients had extracranial complications and Only 2 patients had intracranial complications. 4 patients had facial weakness. All patients were treated with intravenous antibiotic and underwent surgery.**Conclusion:** Otitis media can still result in serious complications in the post antibiotic era due to resistance and over use of antibiotics. Patients with otitis media should be monitored, and surgical intervention should be performed whenever necessary to attain good outcomes. Life threatening complications of COM are still occurring in modern antimicrobial era in developing countries like India because of lack of awareness regarding the symptom like ear discharge and progressive hearing loss.**Keywords:** Complications of CSOM, Mastoiditis, Middle Ear Pathology, Otitis Media.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Chronic otitis media (COM) is persistent inflammation of the middle ear or mastoid cavity. COM is characterized by recurrent or persistent ear discharge (otorrhoea) over 2 to 6 weeks through a perforation of the tympanic membrane. COM usually begins as a complication of persistent acute otitis media (AOM).

Typical findings may also include thickened granular middle-ear mucosa and mucosal polyps. Occasionally, COM will be associated with a cholesteatoma within the middle ear. Cholesteatoma is an abnormal accumulation of squamous epithelium usually found in the middle ear cavity and mastoid process of the temporal bone.

Granulation tissue and ear discharge are often associated with secondary infection of the desquamating epithelium. Cholesteatoma is most often detected by careful otoscopic examination in

children or adults with persistent discharge that does not respond to treatment.

Cholesteatoma [2]

An accumulation of epithelial debris in the middle ear cavity, which can arise congenitally or can be acquired. The tissue is probably derived from skin. It grows slowly but can erode and destroy adjacent structures (ossicles, the mastoid, the inner ear, or the bone leading to the intracranial cavity), potentially leading to persistent pain and otorrhoea, hearing loss, dizziness, facial nerve paralysis, and intracranial infection.

Chronic otitis media (COM) is still common disease in developing country and sometimes difficult to treat. Different complications can develop inspite of availability of higher antibiotics. In pre-antibiotic era, complications of acute otitis media (AOM) and COM were very common and lead to high mortality. In spite of initially decline in

the complication of COM due to higher antibiotics, the incidences are still on rise. COM remains a serious disease, particularly in developing countries and CSOM-related complications are still found life-threatening.

Theories of Spread of Cholesteatoma

Invagination Theory (Retraction Pocket Theory): The most widely accepted theory was proposed by Wittmaack in 1933 and involves invagination or a retraction pocket of the eardrum. This theory claims that the precursors to cholesteatoma are retraction pockets of the pars flaccida, which compared to the pars tensa, is less fibrous and less resistant to displacement. The retraction pocket is caused by negative pressure in the middle ear, which in-turn results from eustachian tube dysfunction (hydrops ex vacuo theory), repeated inflammation, habitual sniffing, or a mastoid of small volume. A deepening of the retraction pocket with accumulation of desquamated keratin can lead to cholesteatoma formation, which obstructs the opening of the pocket and thereby induces ingrowth expansion into the middle ear cleft.

Theory of Epithelial Invasion or Migration (Immigration Theory) Another potential mechanism behind the etiopathogenesis of acquired cholesteatoma is epithelial invasion or migration. This theory was independently proposed by Habermann in 1888¹⁰ and Bezold in 1890, [11] based on their observations obtained during surgery. Immigration theory assumes that the keratinizing squamous epithelium of the eardrum invades or migrates into the middle ear through a traumatic or iatrogenic defect in the eardrum. Immigration theory contradicts the assertion that a

retraction pocket acts as the precursor of acquired cholesteatoma, and was further corroborated in an animal study by Jackson and Lim, [13] who observed migration of keratinizing epithelium into cat bulla by contact guidance.

1. Theory of Squamous Metaplasia: The squamous metaplasia theory was first proposed by Wendt in 1873, who theorized that metaplastic transformation of middle ear mucosa into keratinizing epithelium led to the formation of cholesteatomas. This theory contradicted the simplified and arbitrary definition of acquired cholesteatoma (which described the condition as "skin in the wrong place"), and was widely accepted among otologists in the 19th century.¹⁵ In brief, squamous metaplasia theory stated that an enlargement of cholesteatoma intercurrent with infection and inflammation would lead to lysis and perforation of the eardrum, resulting in the typical appearance of acquired cholesteatoma.

2. Basal Cell Hyperplasia Theory (Papillary Ingrowth Theory): In 1925, the squamous metaplasia theory was challenged by Lange, who proposed the theory of basal cell hyperplasia. Lange theorized that the subepithelial tissue of Prussak's space could be invaded by cholesteatoma microcysts within Shrapnell's membrane (pars flaccida). Prussak's space is a recess bound medially by the neck of malleus, laterally by the pars flaccida, superiorly by the lateral malleolar fold, and inferiorly by the lateral process of malleus. According to basal cell hyperplasia theory, keratin-filled microcysts, buds, or pseudopods are formed in the basal layer of the epithelium, and retraction pockets or eardrum perforations are not necessarily a prerequisite to the formation of cholesteatoma.

Complications of COM

Extra Cranial	Intra Cranial
Intra Temporal	Extradural abscess middle
Persistent TM perforation	Cranial fossa posterior
Mastoiditis Acute coalescent mastoiditis Masked mastoiditis	Cranial fossa
Acute petrositis	Sub dural empyema
Facial paralysis	Meningitis
Labyrinthitis labyrinthine fistula serous labyrinthitis suppurative labyrinthitis	Brain abscess Temporal lobe of cerebrum Cerebellum
Extra Temporal	Lateral sinus thrombophlebitis
Post auricular abscess	CSF otorrhea
Zygomatic abscess	Ottic hydrocephalus
Bezold's abscess	Encephalocele
Meatal abscess (Luc's abscess)	
Behind the mastoid (Citelli's abscess)	
Parapharyngeal and retropharyngeal abscesses	

Methods: All 15 patients of COM with intra or extracranial complication who were admitted in the Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Narendra Modi Medical College Ahmedabad, from April 2023 to April 2024 were included in this retrospective analytic study. All patients underwent detail clinical, otoscopic, microscopic examination.

Hearing assessment was done by pure tone audiometry in all patients. Along with all routine investigations including high resolution computer tomography (HRCT) temporal bone OR MRI was done in every patient. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) brain was done in patients of COM related intracranial complications.

Table 1: Age & Gender Distribution

Age	Present Study 2024 (N=15)			Parmar Bd Et Al 2020 (N=36)		
	Male	Female	No. Of Cases	Male	Female	Total
<10	1	2	3	4	3	7
11-20	2	5	7	10	4	14
21-30		1	1	3	4	7
31-40	-	-	0	3	1	4
41-50	1		1	2	1	3
51-60	1		1	-	1	2
61-70	1	1	2	-	-	-
Total	6	9	15	22	14	36

Table no. 1 suggest age and gender distribution of 15 patients in which 9 patients were female and 6 patients were male. Youngest patient was 9 year old female while oldest patient was 65 year old

female. Highest patients were seen in 11-20 years age group. In comparison to Parmar BD et al 2020 also had highest number of patients of complicated csom in 11 to 20 age group.

Table 2: Symptoms

Symptoms	Recent Study 2024 (N =15)		Harold Heah Study 2016 (N=12)
	No Of Cases	Percentage	
Otalgia	12	80%	75%
Otorrhea	11	73%	58%
Fever	5	33%	41%
Headache	2	13%	25%
Facial Weakness	4	27%	17%
Vertigo	2	13%	

Table no. 2 suggest various symptoms of chronic otitis media in which 80% patients had otalgia ,73% patients had otorrhea, 33% patients had fever,13% patients had headache, 27% patients had facial paralysis. 3 Out of 4 patients who had facial paralysis improved clinically after facial nerve decompression and post-operative physiotherapy. [3]

Table 3: Signs

Signs	Recent Study 2024 (N=15)		Harold Heah Study 2016 (N=12)
	No. of Cases	Percentage	
Swollen Tender Mastoid	7	47%	50%
Inflammatory Polyp	3	20%	41%
Granulations	4	27%	33%
Attic Retraction	9	60%	9%
PSQ Retraction	6	40%	
Facial Palsy	4	27%	
Lateral Rectus Palsy	1	7%	-
Postaural Fistula	4	27%	

Table no. 3 suggest various signs of complicated csom in which 47% patients had swollen and tender mastoiditis in compare to herold heah study 2016 in which 50% patients had this complication .In otoscopic examination 20% had inflammatory polyp, 27% had granulations,60% had attic retraction. [3]

Table 4: Complications

Extra Cranial Complications	Recent Study 2024 (N=15)		Harold Heah Study 2016 (N=12)
	No. Of Cases	Percentage	
Postaural Abscess	6	40%	
Mastoiditis	7	47%	91%
Petrous Apicitis	1	6%	
Facial Paralysis	4	27%	17%
Bezold Abscess	1	7%	
Luc's Abscess	2	13%	
Labyrinthitis	3	20%	
Profound SNHL	3	20%	
Intra Cranial Complications	Recent Study 2024		Harold Health Study 2016
Meningitis	1	6%	
Temporal Lobe Abscess	1	6%	

Table no. 4 suggest various complications of chronic otitis media in which 13% patients had intracranial complications in compared with harold heah study 2016 in which 16% patients had intracranial complications. [3]

Results

- Out of 15 patients 6 were male patients and 9 were female patients.
- We have done HRCT temporal bone in all 15 patients and only 2 patients required MRI BRAIN scan.
- 13 patients had extracranial complications and Only 2 patients had intracranial complications.
- 4 patients had facial weakness
- All patients were treated with intravenous antibiotic and underwent surgery.
- Modified radical mastoidectomy performed in every patients.
- For the 4 patients who had facial nerve palsy concurrent surgical decompression of facial nerve was performed.

- One patient had intra op CSF gush present and repaired with facia lata fat grafting.
- There was no mortality in our case series.
- 2 patients experienced wound dehiscence, which was successfully treated with regular dressing and oral antibiotics.

Discussion

Complications of otitis media may result from acute otitis media or acute exacerbation of chronic otitis media. The reported overall incidence of complications from chronic otitis media ranges from 0.7% to 3.5%. [5,6] In a study conducted by Dubey and Larawin, 85% of the patients with complications arising from chronic suppurative otitis media were aged less than 30 years. [7] and these was also seen in these study. Patients may have had their mastoiditis partially treated with broad-spectrum antibiotics, and present with minimal otological symptoms and vague neurological signs and symptoms; in such cases, Holt and Gates described the clinical entity as 'masked mastoiditis'. [9]

CAVITY DESTRUCTION OF MASTOID BONE ON LEFT SIDE

Figure 1: Cavity destruction of mastoid bone on left side

Complications such as the presence of brain abscess and/or subperiosteal abscess could only be confirmed after imaging.

Thus, we suggest that a thorough otological history be taken and a physical examination performed for patients suspected to have complications of otitis media, especially if they are young or have a compromised immune system. The most common site of brain abscess formation is reported to be the

ipsilateral temporal lobe. [8,10]. In the present study one patient had right temporal lobe abscess. Mastoiditis was the most commonly encountered extracranial complication in the present study. This is not surprising, given that the most direct pathway of middle ear infection extends posteriorly to the mastoid air cells, and no osseous barriers lie in this pathway. Direct extension of the infection can result in subperiosteal abscess formation, as was seen in six of our patients.

FACIAL NERVE DECOMPRESSION

Figure 2: Facial Nerve decompression

Facial nerve palsy was observed in 4 of our patients – all 4 had chronic otitis media with cholesteatoma. Facial nerve palsy in acute otitis media is believed to be a result of oedema of the nerve within the bony canal, compression of cholesteatoma over exposed facial nerve and neuritis. Hence, treatment should be largely conservative, comprising antibiotics, and perhaps myringotomy and grommet tube insertion. [4] In the case of chronic otitis media with facial nerve palsy, early cortical mastoidectomy with careful removal of the diseased tissue around the nerve is advocated. [5] All 4 patients underwent surgical decompression of the facial nerve and had complete recovery.

The role of mastoidectomy in the treatment of otitis media with complications is well established. The purpose would be to determine the underlying pathology (e.g. a previously undiagnosed cholesteatoma) and control the disease process. [10] While the extent of surgery is controversial, canal-wall-up mastoidectomy is advocated by several authors; more radical surgery is reserved for cases with cholesteatoma. [11-13] In the present study, modified radical mastoidectomy was

performed for most of the patients. Despite the advent and accessibility of antibiotic therapy, complications arising from otitis media can still occur in young adults and in developed countries. Although rare, these complications are associated with significant morbidity and even mortality, if diagnosis is not made expeditiously and treatment is not instituted early. A high index of suspicion is needed; clinicians should be vigilant in looking out for swelling in the mastoid region, facial nerve weakness and neurological symptoms such as nausea and vomiting. Early treatment with directed antimicrobial therapy, a multidisciplinary surgical approach that includes mastoidectomy, and, if necessary, neurosurgical intervention (e.g. drainage of brain abscess) allow for good outcomes in patients with complications of otitis media.

Conclusion

Otitis media can still result in serious complications in the post antibiotic era. Patients with otitis media should be monitored, and surgical intervention should be performed when necessary to attain good outcomes. Life threatening complications of COM are still occurring in modern antimicrobial era in

developing countries like India because of lack of awareness regarding the symptom like ear discharge and progressive hearing loss. Inappropriate use of antibiotic treatments may cause masked presentations, thereby causing delay in the diagnosis. For early detection and reference, all clinician should be sensitized regarding the dangerous clinical features of complicated COM. To reduce mortality of complications of COM, early diagnosis of concurrent intracranial complication with HRCT and MRI is required along with proper antibiotic coverage, abscess drainage and mastoid surgery as early as possible.

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